

field trials from 1990 to 1992, it outyielded the check variety (Table 1). In the All India Coordinated Yield Trials, it

ranked 7th out of 81 entries during 1988. Ratnagiri 3 has resistance to gall midge biotypes I and IV and blast disease and

moderate resistance to stem borer, bacterial leaf blight, sheath blight, and brown spot (Table 2). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Gan wan Xian 23 (Gan You Wan, SG89320): a new indica rice variety with high quality

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Gan wan Xian 23, released in May 1994 by the Jiangxi Provincial Seed Board, is a new semidwarf indica rice variety with high quality and other good traits. It was derived from the cross between IR841 and M79215, which is a strain from the cross Xi Dao 1/5450. The F_3 was irradiated with ^{60}Co γ -rays at the dose of 30 krad.

Gan wan Xian 23 is suitable for the later season in the double-cropped area of southern China and single-cropped area of central China. Because of its high quality, it won the gold medal prize at the First China Agriculture Exposition, sponsored by the Ministry of Agriculture in Oct 1992. In the double-cropped area, its average yield was 4.9-5.3 t/ha, which was 15% more than that of Shung Zhu Zheng, a check being used for the new high-quality evaluation in southern China. In the single-cropped area, the average yield of Gan wan Xian 23 was 5.3-6 t/ha.

The variety has strong stems, is 92-105 cm tall, and has a growth duration of 135-140 d. Gan wan Xian 23 has high yield potential under good irrigation and management conditions. It performed

Major quality traits of Gan wan Xian 23. Rice Research Institute of China, 1992.

Brown rice (%)	78-80.2
Milled rice recovery (%)	63-66.3
Head rice (%)	58-63
Kernel length (mm)	6.7
L:W ratio	3.3
Chalky kernel (%)	0
Area with chalkiness (%)	0
Amylose content (%)	15
Alkali spreading value	6.9
Gel consistency (mm)	90
Protein content of head rice (%)	7.0

well in regional trials, with yield reaching 6.3 t/ha in Hu Bei Province.

Gan wan Xian 23 has good resistance to blast disease. It has long, slender, translucent grains with intermediate amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and soft gel consistency (see table). The cooked rice of Gan wan Xian 23 is soft and aromatic.

It has a 1,000 grain weight of 23-25.7 g, panicle length of 21.5-29.3 cm, and

88.7-116 field grains/panicle (82.5-91.8%). Gan wan Xian 23 is very popular among consumers in Hongkong. Its quality is at par with the high-quality Thai rices. Gan wan Xian 23 is being grown in Jiangxi, Hubei, Guangdong, Anhui, and Guanxi provinces, and is spreading quickly in other provinces of southern and central China. ■

Heibao, a high-yielding, good quality black indica rice for China

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Heibao is a newly released semidwarf indica variety with a black pericarp. It is derived from Dong-Lan-Mo-Mi/IR64 and has a 108-112 d duration. Heibao is highly cold tolerant at the seedling stage and is resistant to blast and bacterial blight. During the 1993 early season in Zhejiang, Jiangxi, Hubei, and Anhui, blast attacked many rice varieties but not Heibao. It has wide adaptability as an early rice in the double-cropped Yangtze River area.

Average yield at eight locations was 6.8 t/ha in 1993. The highest yield,

9.0 t/ha, was 25-40% more than the yields of the local black rice check varieties. Heibao has a 1,000-grain weight of 21.2 g, with 90% seed fertility.

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, cooking, and eating quality meet China's national index for high quality rice. Heibao's grain quality is superior to that of most black pericarp indica varieties in China. Grain length is 7.0 mm, with a 3.2 length-breadth ratio. Hulling recovery is 79%; milling recovery, 70.2%; and head rice recovery, 53%. Grain is semitranslucent with 19.3% amylose and 10.4% protein content. Four percent of the grain is chalky, with 0.2% area with chalkiness. It has intermediate gelatinization temperature and gel consistency (5.6 mm). Fe, P, Se, and other minerals are 3-5 times greater in Heibao than in ordinary rice. ■

Peiliangyou Teqing, a new high-yielding, two-line hybrid rice

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Peiliangyou Teqing (Pei'ai 64S/Teqing), developed by HHRRC, passed the examination of the Crop Variety Release Committee of Hunan Province in Jan 1994. It is the first two-line hybrid rice combination approved at the

provincial level for release to farmers in China.

Pei'ai 64S, the maternal parent, is a thermosensitive genic male sterile line bred from Nongken 58S/Pei'ai 64//Pei'ai 64. It shows pollen sterility of 99.98% and seed sterility of 100% based on a 50-panicle sample of 1,150 plants in 1990. It has a long sterile period: about 20 d at Shengyang, Beijing, and Guiyang; more than 50 d at Changsha; and nearly 80 d at Guangzhou—and even longer at Hainan.

Table 1. Comparison of grain yield between Peiliangyou Teqing and check Shanyou 63. HRVRT, Hunan, China, 1992-93.

Year	Locations (no.)	Combinations and varieties (no.)	Replications (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Peiliangyou Teqing over check ^a	
				Peiliangyou Teqing	Shanyou 63	t/ha	%
1992	7	6	3	9.5	9.1	0.43**	4.7
1993	6	9	3	7.7	7.3	0.43 ^{ns}	5.8

^a** = significant at 1% level by Duncan's SSR test; ns = not significant by Duncan's SSR test.

Table 2. Economic traits and grain quality of Peiliangyou Teqing. HRVRT, Hunan, China, 1992-93.

Year	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Chalkiness (%)
1992	136.7	97.5	140.1	87.9	23.4	79.4	69.8	45.6	5.3
1993	135.8	105.6	144.5	84.6	22.3	82.8	70.6	62.2	-
Mean	136.3	101.6	142.3	86.3	22.9	81.1	70.2	53.9	5.3

Pei'ai 64S has a low critical sterility temperature of 23.3 °C under short daylength. When the daily mean temperature is more than 23.3 °C, it is completely sterile; when the daily mean temperature is less than 23.3 °C, it becomes partially fertile, thus producing selfed seeds. It has also wide compatibility, and when crossed with either indica or japonica rices, it shows generally normal pollen and seed fertility in the F₁ hybrids. Because Pei'ai 64S has a low critical sterility temperature (23.3 °C under short daylength), it is difficult to multiply. Yield during seed multiplication was usually unstable because of fluctuating temperatures, but more than 2.25 t/ha may be obtained by irrigating with low-temperature water.

Teqing, the paternal line, is a high-yielding indica variety developed by the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences and being grown in southern China.

In the 1992 Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trial (HRVRT) for medium rice, Peiliangyou Teqing yielded an average of 9.5 t/ha across seven locations (Table 1), 4.7% (significant at 1% level) higher than the check hybrid Shanyou 63 and the best of six combinations or varieties tested. In the 1993 HRVRT, its yield averaged 7.7 t/ha across six locations, 5.8% higher than that of Shanyou 63 and the best of nine combinations or varieties tested.

The combination was cultivated in demonstration plots in 1991. Planted on 667 ha in 1992 and 1,333 ha in 1993 in Hunan Province, it yielded 7.5-9.0 t/ha.

Jinuo 1: a new glutinous japonica variety with high yield and good quality

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Jinuo 1 is a new glutinous japonica rice variety derived from JG954 (58nuo/Nonghu 6//BL-7) using the system selection method. It was released in Mar 1992 as a special rice variety.

Jinuo 1 is photoperiod-insensitive and has a 170 d growth duration. It is 100 cm tall, with panicle length of 16.5 cm, and a 1,000-grain weight of 28 g. Its fertility is more than 85%. The yield potential of Jinuo 1 is high and stable, 0.9-32.6%

Yield potential of Jinuo 1 in the Rice Regional Trials of northern China, 1992.

Site	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check ^a (%)
Beijing	7.5	23.4
Zhuozhou, Hebei	9.5	32.6
Tianjin	8.0	7.32
Baoding, Hebei	10.6	31.78
Tanghai, Hebei	8.9	0.9
Liaoning	5.3	1.15

^aZhonghua 8.

The combination matures in 136 d as a medium rice crop (Table 2). It is moderately resistant to blast and bacterial blight. Peiliangyou Teqing is about 100 cm tall and has good plant type, strong tillering ability, sturdy stature, dark green leaves, and large panicles. Its seed setting rate is more than 80%, with a mean of 142 spikelets/panicle and a 1,000-grain weight of 23 g. The yields of brown, milled, and head rice were 81.1%, 70.2%, and 53.9%, respectively. Chalkiness was 5.3% and the eating quality acceptable. ■

more than the check in the Rice Regional Trials of northern China in 1992. Its yield stability was the best among the new varieties being tested (see table).

Jinuo 1 is moderately resistant to leaf blast and bacterial blight and is resistant to whitebacked planthopper. Its resistance to lodging is very strong because of its firm stems.

Most of the grain quality characteristics of Jinuo 1 meet China's national index for good quality rice. Hulling recovery was 84.5%; milling recovery, 76.0%; grain length, 5.1 mm; grain length-breadth ratio, 1.6; amylose content, 1.2%; and protein content, 7.4%.

Jinuo 1 is planted on about 6,000 ha. It is the first time that a high-yielding glutinous japonica rice variety with good quality was selected in northern China. ■